

Germplasm improvement

Breeding methods

Heterotic hybrid combinations identified for commercial exploitation of hybrid vigor in rice

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We attempted to identify some elite hybrid combinations by crossing three cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines, V20 A, IR58025 A, and IR62829 A, with 33 known restorer lines from Indian germplasm. The 99 F₁s produced using line × tester design were evaluated along with 36 parental lines during 1992 wet season (WS) at the Directorate of Rice Research (DRR), Hyderabad.

The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design. Each entry was replicated three times. Hybrids and parents were transplanted in rows of 20 plants at 20 × 15-cm spacing and fertilizer applied at 100-60-40 kg NPK/ha following recommended practices. We recorded days to 50% flowering for each replication of each culture. Grain yield per plant was assessed by taking the mean yield of five randomly selected plants in each replication.

Twenty-two of the cross combinations exhibited standard heterosis of >20% over the check, Jaya (see table). Among the hybrids tested using V20 A as the female, V20 A/UPR254-85-ITCA showed high standard heterosis (42.4%) over Jaya. We identified 13 heterotic cross combinations using IR58025 A as the female (see table). IR62829 A/Chianungsenyu, IR62829 A/Mahsuri, and IR62829 A/Vajram were the best among the crosses using IR62829 A as the female.

Performance of elite rice hybrids showing yield heterosis of >20% over Jaya. DRR, Hyderabad, India, 1992 WS.

Cross	Days to 50% flowering $\bar{X}$	Grain yield/plant (g)	
		$\bar{X}$	Standard heterosis over Jaya (%)
V20 A/Vajram (MTU5249)	91	19.6	24.2** ^a
V20 A/Iri 316 R	91	19.2	21.5**
V20 A/IR2797-125	93	21.8	37.9**
V20 A/UPR254-85-ITCA	81	22.6	42.4**
IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R	101	22.4	41.1**
IR58025 A/Vajram (MTU5249)	92	24.0	51.8**
IR58025 A/IR13419-13-10 R	100	19.6	22.8**
IR58025 A/IR28178-70-2-3	101	21.9	38.7**
IR58025 A/Chianungsenyu	90	20.4	29.1**
IR58025 A/Suweon 318 R	96	24.0	51.8**
IR58025 A/ARC 11353 R	101	23.0	45.6**
IR58025 A/Suweon 287 R	108	27.8	75.9**
IR58025 A/HKR119	93	20.9	32.3**
IR58025 A/NST200	99	24.1	52.5**
IR58025 A/BR51-91-7	84	19.5	23.4**
IR58025 A/T1154	79	22.3	41.3**
IR58025 A/IET9188	100	22.8	44.3**
IR62829 A/Vajram (MTU5249)	92	22.3	40.8**
IR62829 A/IR13419-13-10R	94	20.5	29.8**
IR62829 A/IR35366-40-3-3	87	20.8	31.6**
IR62829 A/Chianungsenyu	87	26.9	68.4**
IR62829 A/Mahsuri	98	25.7	62.8**
Jaya (check)	97	15.8	—

*** = Significant at the 1% level.

IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R, IR58025 A/IR13419-13-10 R, IR58025 A/IR28178-70-2-3, IR58025 A/Suweon 287 R, and IR58025 A/IET9188 mature in about 130 d, making them medium-

duration hybrids. The rest are short-duration. Commercially exploiting these 22 F₁ hybrids should be quite worthwhile because of their >20% mean grain yield advantage over Jaya. ■

Tropical japonica lines as improved sources of wide compatibility trait in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Indica/japonica or indica/tropical japonica F₁ hybrids, though heterotic, exhibit high spikelet sterility that hinders their commercial exploitation. Allelic interaction at the S₅ locus, which leads to partial elimination of female gametes carrying japonica alleles, causes indica/japonica sterility. Some rice cultivars, however, exhibit normal fertility when

crossed to both indica or japonica lines. They are called wide compatible varieties (WCVs). During the past decade, several WCVs — mostly traditional varieties — have been identified in Japan, at IRRI, and in China.

To break the present yield plateau, efforts are being made to develop a new plant type involving crosses with tropical japonica (previously known as *bulu*) germplasm.

Experiments at IRRI have shown that tropical japonica lines, when crossed with semidwarf indica rices, exhibit stronger yield heterosis than do indica/indica hybrids provided that either of the